

Snell's Law and X, T Independence in the Classical Action

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 23, 2022

Snell's law of refraction may be derived in a number of ways. In (1) these approaches include: Fermat's principle, Huygen's principle, electromagnetism and conservation of energy and momentum. In a previous note (1) we argued that a free particle classical action (relativistic or nonrelativistic i.e. $-m_0 \int \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} dt$ or $\int .5mv^2 dt$) may be written in terms of $v=x/t$ and x and t varied independently to yield: $dA/dx = p$ and $dA/dt = -E$. From this $A = -Et + px$ with x and t independent. If one writes eigenvalue equations, then $\exp(iA)$ is a solution. We argue that a photon moving from one medium into another does not lose energy. Thus $\exp(-iEt)$ represents a kind of cycling in each medium which we take to be the same. In other words if we consider t medium 1 = t medium 2 and also consider either vertical or horizontal motion by itself then d medium 1 = v (medium 1) t and d (medium 2) = v (medium 2) t . In other words a constant Et action in each medium leads to different horizontal and vertical lengths. These may be shown to yield Snell's law, we argue. If one uses the angled light then constant $-Et$ leads to different lengths L_1 and L_2 and does readily yield information about refraction.

Snell's Law and Various Derivations

Snell's law states that:

$$\sin(\theta_1) / \sin(\theta_2) = n_2 / n_1 \quad \text{where } n \text{ is the index of refraction.} \quad ((1))$$

θ_1 is the incident angle in an n_1 medium measured against a vertical and θ_2 the refracted angle also measured against a vertical line. It should be noted that $v_1 = c/n_1$ in n_1 and $v_2 = c/n_2$ in n_2 . Thus for water or glass which have a higher index of refraction than air, the speed of light is slower. Also the component of momentum parallel to the surface is $k_1 \text{ parallel} = k_2 \text{ parallel}$ with $k_i = n_i \omega / c$ where ω is angular frequency and c the speed of light in a vacuum as stated in (1). Overall $p_1 = \omega / c (1/n_1)$ and $v_1 = c/n_1$ so that $E = p_1 v_1$ is a constant.

Snell's law may be derived in a number of ways as outlined in (1). In particular it may be obtained through Fermat's principle i.e. by minimizing time or by Huygen's principle using circular waves. It may also be obtained through Maxwell's electromagnetic equations by considering a tiny box with almost zero vertical sides along the interface. The electric field $\exp(i k x)$ for such a tiny box becomes $1 + i k x$ and one has $k_i \text{ parallel} = n_i \omega / c$. $k_i \text{ parallel} = k_i \text{ overall} \sin(\theta_i)$ and $k_i \text{ overall} = \omega / c (1/n_i)$.

Snell's law may also be obtained by conservation of momentum as argued in (1). This approach is almost identical to the electromagnetic one because one argues that:

$$k_1 \text{ parallel} = k_2 \text{ parallel} \rightarrow k_1 \text{ overall} \sin(\theta_1) = k_2 \text{ overall} \sin(\theta_2) \quad \text{where } k_i \text{ overall} = n_i \omega / c.$$

Classical Action Approach and x and t Independent

Here we suggest an alternative approach to obtaining Snell's law. We consider a free particle classical action which is:

$$A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1) \text{ relativistic} \quad \text{or} \quad A = t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 \text{ nonrelativistic} \quad ((2))$$

If one sets $v=x/t$ and treats x and t as independent then:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} = p \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = -E \quad \text{suggesting} \quad A = -Et + px \quad ((3))$$

Writing ((3)) in terms of eigenvalue equations yields:

$$-i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad \text{and} \quad i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((4))$$

$A = -Et + px$ applies to both a classical particle and classical wave. For the wave:

$$dA=0 = -E dt + p dx \quad \text{and for the particle} \quad dA=0 = -t dE/dp + x.$$

From ((1)) $p_{\text{horizontal}} = w/c \cdot n_1$ and one knows that $v_1=c/n_1$ so E associated with horizontal motion is: $p_{\text{horizontal}} \cdot v_1 = E = p_2 \cdot v_2$.

According to the $x - t$ independent scenario $\exp(-iEt)$ (the time part of the eigenfunction) is not bothered by motion in one medium or another for horizontal motion.. The cycling (frequency in time) seems to stay the same. If one considers $t_{\text{medium 1}} = t_{\text{medium 2}}$ for the horizontal part of the motion so that $-E t_1 = -E t_2$ i.e. the time part of the action remains constant then

$$D_1 (\text{horizontal}) = c/n_1 t \quad \text{and} \quad d_2 (\text{horizontal}) = c/n_2 t \quad ((5))$$

Thus they travel different distances. At this point it is as if one has a separate problem with only horizontal motion. One wishes to link this to the problem of an angled ray (θ_1) in n_1 moving into medium n_2 . We argue that the different distances in ((5)) suggest different distances in n_1 and n_2 in the following way. If one considers the same angled L for motion with θ_1 and θ_2 then: $d_1 (\text{horizontal}) = L \sin(\theta_1)$ and $d_2 (\text{horizontal}) = L \sin(\theta_2)$.

One may note that the overall time along L in each medium is not the same i.e. $L=c/n_1 t_1$ and $L=c/n_2 t_2$ with t_1 and t_2 not being the same. For the overall angled light, applying a constant time portion of the action i.e. $-Et$ leads to two different L values i.e. L_1 and L_2 and does not give information about refraction.

Then ((5)) yields:

$\sin(\theta_1) / \sin(\theta_2) = n_2/n_1$ or Snell's law ((6))

What about the two vertical distances? Those lead to the same result, but with $\cos(\theta_1)$ written as $\sin(90 \text{ degrees} - \theta_2)$. Thus ((5)) suggests that refraction occurs and allows for one to compute it.

Conclusion

Snell's law may be derived in a number of ways as outlined in (1). Here we argue that the classical action may be written as $A = -Et + px$ for both a classical particle and a wave. If one wishes to have an eigenvalue equation then $\exp(iA)$ is a solution. These results hold for x and t treated as independent. Given that $E=pc$ if one considers a problem with only horizontal motion, then $v_1=c/n_1$ and $p_1= w/c (n_1)$ so that E is the same for 1 and 2. To keep the time part of the action the same i.e. $-Et$ region 1 = $-E t$ region 2 one has the same time, but this leads to different distances for the horizontal component of motion namely:

$D_1 = c/n_1 t$ and $d_2 = c/n_2 t$.

We argue that these different distances apply to a problem with an angled light ray (θ_1) moving from n_1 to n_2 . Thus, if one uses $d_1 = L\sin(\theta_1)$ and $d_2 = L \sin(\theta_2)$ one obtains Snell's law.

One may use the vertical component of motion, but then one must use $\cos(\theta_1) = \sin(90 \text{ deg} - \theta_1)$ i.e. the angle is measured with respect to the horizontal not vertical. This is like performing a 90 degree rotation.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)